

DETECT PLANT DISEASE USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

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Abstract— Agriculture is vital to the economy but faces challenges from weather changes and rising plant diseases. Early detection of these diseases is crucial for preserving crop yields and livelihoods. However, manual identification is prone to errors, prompting the need for precise methods. Advanced image processing, like CNNs, offers a solution. By analyzing leaf images, CNN algorithms accurately identify diseases. This project aims to improve disease detection using CNNs, guiding farmers in selecting effective insecticides. Through machine learning, it aims to boost crop yields, ease economic burdens, and promote sustainable agriculture in India.

Keywords—*PlantDisease, CNN, Tensorflow and Keras, PIL, deep Learning*

I. INTRODUCTION

India's agricultural sector, vital for the economy and the livelihoods of over 60% of the population, faces escalating challenges due to changing weather patterns and increasing incidences of plant diseases. This has led to significant drops in crop yields and financial strain for farmers. Early disease detection is challenging, making it difficult to control outbreaks effectively. However, technology, particularly in image processing and machine learning, offers hope for sustainable farming.

Plant diseases can range in severity from minor leaf or fruit damage to total crop death, and they can be caused by a variety of organisms, including bacteria, fungus, or viruses. Black spot, powdery mildew, Fusarium wilt, gray mold, leaf blight, white mold, scab, and fire blight are examples of common plant diseases. For this experiment, Mendeleev Data was used to gather leaf photos, and CNN was used to extract disease information from the images. Furthermore, farmer-friendly automated solutions were created with the goal of boosting resilience and food security by offering prompt support and guidance. India can enhance its ability to combat plant diseases and advance sustainable farming methods by using technology into agriculture.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Malvika Ranjan and associates et al. [1] begin their study of plant leaf disease detection with picture capture. The segmentation findings are used to extract color data, such as HSV characteristics, and these features are then used to train an artificial neural network (ANN) to distinguish between samples that are healthy and those that are sick. This work proposes an approach to accurately and early detect cotton

leaf diseases by combining ann with image data processing techniques.

In a study by Vaishnavi Monigari, G. Khyathi, T. Prathima, et al. [2], the CNN was trained using a dataset of more than 20,000 photos of both healthy and diseased plant leaves, which were categorized into 15 groups. The OpenCV framework was utilized for image processing, and to enhance the quantity of images in the dataset, image augmentation was applied. The created model could differentiate between eight illnesses and healthy leaves with 90% accuracy.

In the research paper “Plant Disease Detection using Image Processing,” authored by Mr.V Suresh, D Gopinath, M Hemavarthini, K Jayanthan, and Mohana Krishnan, et al. [3] the focus is on the precise identification of diseased and healthy plants. This study utilizes a vast collection of plant disease images for accurate detection. The methodology involves an Android application designed to identify plant diseases efficiently. By leveraging the power of convolutional neural networks (CNN) and sophisticated algorithms, this research aims at recognizing various species and diseases affecting crop leaves. The integration of technology and botany in this paper offers promising advancements in agricultural disease management.

Pushkara Sharma, Pankaj Hans, Subhash Chand Gupta, et al. [4] employed a dataset of more than 2000 photos that were split up into 19 distinct classifications. Noise was removed using Gaussian Blur, and pictures were preprocessed by converting RGB to HSV. For segmentation, K-means clustering was employed. Four classifiers—KNN, CNN, SVM, and logistic regression—were examined. At 98%, the CNN classifier demonstrated the highest accuracy.

Using image processing and learning approaches, Marwan Adanan Jasim and Jamal Mustafa AL-Tuwaijari et al. [5] concentrated on plant leaf disease detection and classification for tomato, pepper, and potato leaves. CNN was utilized to classify the dataset, which included over 20,000 photos. There were 12 classes for damaged leaves and 3 classes for healthy leaves. For the training dataset, the model's accuracy was 98.29%, and for the testing dataset, it was 98.029%.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the provided project, which focuses on detecting plant diseases using a Convolutional Neural

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Network (CNN) with TensorFlow and Keras, can be outlined in the following steps:

A. Data Collection: The project utilizes a comprehensive dataset of plant leaves affected by various diseases, along with healthy specimens, to train the CNN model. The dataset is meticulously organized into different folders, each representing a specific plant disease or healthy condition. This extensive collection ensures the diversity and representativeness needed for accurate disease identification.

B. Data preprocessing: Data preprocessing involves resizing images to a uniform dimension of 256x256 pixels to ensure consistent input size for the CNN. The images are then normalized by scaling the pixel values to a range of 0 to 1. This normalization is crucial for the efficient training of the neural network. An advanced data augmentation technique is employed, generating additional training data through transformations like rotation, width and height shifting, shear, zoom, and horizontal flipping. These transformations enhance the model's robustness by simulating various angles and conditions of leaf presentation.

C. Transfer Learning : The model architecture comprises an input layer followed by convolutional layers with ReLU activation functions, interspersed with max-pooling layers to reduce spatial dimensions. After the convolutional base, the model includes a flattening step to transform the 2D feature maps into 1D feature vectors, followed by dense layers with ReLU activation for high-level reasoning and a final softmax layer for multi-class classification. This architecture is optimized for extracting and learning hierarchical feature representations of the plant leaves.

In addition to building a CNN from scratch, the project employs transfer learning by utilizing a pre-trained model as the foundational architecture. This approach involves fine-tuning the final layers of a pre-existing network trained on a large dataset, such as ImageNet, to adapt to the specific task of plant disease classification. Transfer learning significantly enhances the model's ability to recognize complex patterns with a relatively smaller dataset, improving accuracy and reducing the time required for training.

D. Model Training : The provided code enables the training of a convolutional neural network (CNN) to distinguish between healthy and diseased plants and classify them into 38 different categories, leveraging a pre processed and augmented dataset split into training and validation sets. With 61,486 images in the training data and 15,572 images in the validation data, the training process focuses on tuning the model to minimize a categorical cross-entropy loss function. The Adam optimizer is utilized for efficient iterative optimization. To assess the generalization ability of the model, its performance is evaluated on a separate test set not seen by the model during training. Metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and Cohen's Kappa are calculated, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the model's ability to accurately classify various plant diseases.

E. Model Deployment : A user-friendly graphical interface, developed using Tkinter, enables users to easily upload images of plant leaves for disease diagnosis, making the disease detection model accessible for practical use. This application, with its functionalities for image uploading, real-

time prediction, and result display, seamlessly integrates with the trained model.

The model, saved for future use, ensures immediate and efficient plant disease diagnosis within the application. This strategic preservation of the model's learning capacity not only facilitates its integration into the disease detection application but also ensures its utility for ongoing and future applications in plant health management. By incorporating Transfer Learning and deploying the model through a user-centric interface, this methodology highlights an innovative blend of deep learning advancements with practical solutions, addressing real-world challenges in agriculture and plant disease management effectively.

Fig1: System Architecture

IV. BUILD MODEL

The cornerstone of effective plant disease diagnosis through image processing lies in constructing a robust and precise machine learning model. This seminar paper delineates the development of such a model, employing classification techniques within the TensorFlow and Keras frameworks. By harnessing a sophisticated convolutional neural network (CNN), we aim to achieve high accuracy in identifying various plant diseases.

Importing Libraries

Pandas, Numpy, TensorFlow, and other Machine Learning libraries are defined as an interface of a set of rules built in a particular language to conduct repetitive work such as arithmetic computations, reading photos, and so

```

[76]: import numpy as np
import os
import tensorflow as tf
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import operator
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, accuracy_score,
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import img_to_array,
from tensorflow.keras import layers
from tensorflow.keras import Model
from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model
from tensorflow.image import rgb_to_grayscale
    
```

Training the Model

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Training the model using the method.

```
[85]: from tensorflow.keras.layers import Input, Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense
      from tensorflow.keras.models import Model

      # Define the input layer
      inputs = Input(shape=(64, 64, 3))

      # Define the rest of the model
      x = Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='relu')(inputs)
      x = MaxPooling2D((2, 2))(x)
      x = Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu')(x)
      x = MaxPooling2D((2, 2))(x)
      x = Flatten()(x)
      x = Dense(128, activation='relu')(x)
      outputs = Dense(39, activation='softmax')(x)

      # Create the model
      model = Model(inputs, outputs)

[86]: model.compile(
      optimizer='adam',
      loss='sparse_categorical_crossentropy',
      metrics=['accuracy']
    )

    epochs = 30 # You can increase this for better performance

    batch_size = 32

[87]: history = model.fit(X_train, Y_train, epochs=epochs, batch_size=batch_size, validation_split=0.33)
```



```
matrix = confusion_matrix(Y_test, Y_predict)
tp = matrix[1, 1]
fp = matrix[0, 1]
tn = matrix[0, 0]
fn = matrix[1, 0]

recall = tp / (tp + fn)
specificity = tn / (tn + fp)
precision = tp / (tp + fp)
f1 = 2 * (precision * recall) / (precision + recall)
kappa = (accuracy - (1 - accuracy)) / (1 - (1 - accuracy))

1442/1442 ----- 35s 24ms/step - accuracy: 0.9862 - loss: 0.0708
train Loss: 0.2668
train Accuracy: 0.9582
481/481 ----- 9s 19ms/step - accuracy: 0.8701 - loss: 0.8203
Test Loss: 0.8042
Test Accuracy: 0.8748
Model Name: CNN1
481/481 ----- 9s 17ms/step
Test Accuracy = 0.8748
[[ 147  8  0 ...  1  0  0]
 [  0 192  2 ...  2  0  0]
 [  0  0 208 ...  0  2  0]
 ...
 [  0  4  0 ... 188  1  0]
 [  0  0  1 ...  0 1226  0]
 [  0  0  0 ...  1  0 356]]
True Positives: 192
False Positives: 8
True Negatives: 147
False Negatives: 0
Recall: 1.0
Specificity: 0.9483870967741935
Precision: 0.96
F1 Score: 0.9795918367346939
Cohen's Kappa: 0.8568453930244664
Parameters: 1630183.0000
```

V. RESULT
 Accuracy

Accuracy of the algorithm

```
history = model.fit(X_train, Y_train, epochs=epochs, batch_size=batch_size, validation_split=0.33)

Epoch 1/30
966/966 ----- 78s 77ms/step - accuracy: 0.4840 - loss: 1.9266 - val_accuracy: 0.7695 - val_loss: 0.7431
Epoch 2/30
966/966 ----- 72s 74ms/step - accuracy: 0.8181 - loss: 0.5941 - val_accuracy: 0.8385 - val_loss: 0.5154
Epoch 3/30
966/966 ----- 69s 71ms/step - accuracy: 0.8835 - loss: 0.3664 - val_accuracy: 0.8570 - val_loss: 0.4478
Epoch 4/30
966/966 ----- 70s 72ms/step - accuracy: 0.9211 - loss: 0.2475 - val_accuracy: 0.8743 - val_loss: 0.4013
Epoch 5/30
966/966 ----- 69s 71ms/step - accuracy: 0.9437 - loss: 0.1787 - val_accuracy: 0.8855 - val_loss: 0.3970
Epoch 6/30
966/966 ----- 70s 72ms/step - accuracy: 0.9585 - loss: 0.1280 - val_accuracy: 0.8853 - val_loss: 0.4048
Epoch 7/30
966/966 ----- 70s 72ms/step - accuracy: 0.9691 - loss: 0.0933 - val_accuracy: 0.8784 - val_loss: 0.4650
Epoch 8/30
966/966 ----- 69s 72ms/step - accuracy: 0.9722 - loss: 0.0807 - val_accuracy: 0.9008 - val_loss: 0.3872
```

Plant Disease Detection

```
[86]: model.compile(
      optimizer='adam',
      loss='sparse_categorical_crossentropy',
      metrics=['accuracy']
    )

    epochs = 30 # You can increase this for better performance

    batch_size = 32

[87]: history = model.fit(X_train, Y_train, epochs=epochs, batch_size=batch_size, validation_split=0.33)
```


Implementation

```
import tkinter as tk
from tkinter import ttk, filedialog
import cv2
import PIL.Image, PIL.ImageTk
import numpy as np
from keras.models import load_model
from keras.preprocessing.image import img_to_array
import os

class LeafDiseaseDetectorApp:
    def __init__(self, master):
        self.master = master
        master.title('Leaf Disease Detector')
        self.headline_label = ttk.Label(master, text="AgriAlert - Plant Disease Detector",
                                       font=('Helvetica', 25, 'bold'), foreground='white')
        self.headline_label.place(relx=0.5, rely=0.05, anchor='center')

        self.model_path = r"C:\Users\DELL\Desktop\sneha\project\leafmodel.h5" # Update to your model's path
        self.target_size = (64, 64)
        self.class_labels = {0: "Apple__Apple_scab",
                              1: "Apple__Black_rot",
                              2: "Apple__cedar_apple_rust",
                              3: "Apple__healthy",
                              4: "Background_without_leaves",
                              5: "Blueberry__healthy",
                              6: "Cherry__Powdery_mildew",
                              7: "Cherry__healthy",
                              8: "Corn__Cercospora_leaf_spot Gray_leaf_spot",

                              .....

        print("No image on camera found.")

    def process_and_predict(self, image):
        image = cv2.resize(image, self.target_size)
        image = img_to_array(image) / 255.0
        image = np.expand_dims(image, axis=0)
        predictions = self.model.predict(image)
        predicted_class_index = np.argmax(predictions, axis=1)
        predicted_class_label = self.class_labels.get(predicted_class_index[0], "Unknown")
        return predicted_class_label

    def quit(self):
        if self.camera is not None:
            self.camera.release()
        self.master.destroy()

def main():
    root = tk.Tk()
    root.geometry("1000x1000") # Adjust as needed
    app = LeafDiseaseDetectorApp(root)
    root.mainloop()

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

Based on the dataset provided the plant disease can be identified and a small description of what the disease is provided and the cure is recommended. We can determine the plant disease by uploading the image of the disease affected plant leaf. First we have to upload the image of the leaf which is affected by the disease in figure 2 and press the detect button as shown in figure 3.

Fig 2: Upload the image

Fig 3: Detected Output

VI. CONCLUSION

The paper provides a method to detect plant leaf disease using Convolutional Neural Network. Here primarily we teach the system various common diseases that may occur to the leaf. The dataset contains various class of diseases. When the input image is uploaded the image is compared with the dataset and the most accurate result will be provided. The most matching result will be considered as the output disease. The system is very helpful for automated disease detection.

VII. REFERENCES

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